

Milestone MS13

The Compliance Framework for the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)

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Log of changes

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1. Executive Summary

This document describes a Compliance Framework for the GDI project. It gives an overview of the components of the Compliance Framework and explains how it facilitates continued improvements of the GDI processes, striving for excellence and building trust.

Due to the broad heterogeneity across GDI nodes the path towards SOP compliance is broken down into individual steps to offer guidance and enable all nodes to engage with the Compliance Framework, regardless of the individual node's level of maturity. Templates are provided to capture staff training records and to document a compliance assessment.

2. Glossary

Acronyms	Meaning
Activities ¹	A set of actions carried out within a process
Audit ¹	Systematic, independent and documented process for obtaining audit evidence and evaluating it objectively to determine the extent to which the audit criteria are fulfilled
FitSM ²	Free and lightweight standards aimed at facilitating service management in IT service provision, including federated scenarios.
GDI	European Genomic Data Infrastructure
ISO ³	International Organisation for Standardisation
certification ⁴	The provision by an independent body of written assurance (a certificate) that the product, service or system in question meets specific requirements.
MS	Milestone
OC ⁵	Operations Committee
Policy ¹	Documented set of intentions, expectations, goals, rules and requirements, often formally expressed by top management representatives in an organisation or federation Note: Policies are then realised in processes, which are in turn made up of activities that people carry out according to defined procedures.
Procedure ¹	Specified set of steps or instructions to be carried out by an individual or group to perform one or more activities of a process
Process ¹	Structured set of activities, with clearly defined responsibilities, that bring about a specific objective or set of results from a set of defined inputs
SDPC ⁵	Security and Data Protection Committee
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure

¹ FitSM definitions: ITEM0 e.V. (2025). FitSM-0: Overview and vocabulary (Version 3.0.1). Retrieved from <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/>.

² <https://www.fitsm.eu/fitsm-standard/>

³ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

⁴ <https://www.iso.org/certification.html>

⁵ GDI MS10: <https://zenodo.org/records/7947684/files/GDI%20MS10-1.pdf>

3. Introduction

The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) is a EC-funded project with 70 partner institutes from 24 European countries aiming to set up a European infrastructure with national nodes across the participating member states. Such an enormous multinational effort comes with its challenges, not just on a governance level but also in the heterogeneity of the participating nodes. Those nodes with the most mature GDI services aim to become operational by April 2026, while others are still in the process of setting up their infrastructures. Some nodes are linked to existing infrastructures that operate according to, or are certified against, a recognised quality management system. Other nodes are based within an academic environment or are establishing new services and infrastructures with little experience in a compliance framework.

Initially, milestone 13 was envisaged as a first compliance assessment across the GDI nodes to be performed in April 2025. This compliance assessment would evaluate if the processes within an operational node would conform to the existing SOPs, policies and other relevant requirements like regulations. In Amendment 4 of the Grant Agreement from 2025, milestone 13 was postponed by six months due to the delay in GDI nodes becoming operational. As of October 2025, no GDI node is currently operational, hence it is still too early to perform a meaningful compliance assessment. To avoid further delays, it was decided to produce a guidance document which defines a Compliance Framework for compliance assessments of GDI nodes in the future. This document will then form the basis for milestone 14, the compliance assessment to be performed in 2026.

This guidance document aims to provide practical information for all nodes to help them progress from any maturity level.

4. The Importance of a Compliance Framework

Defining Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and Policies is crucial to ensure that processes are consistent, compatible across systems and organisations. This is especially important in highly complex settings such as GDI, where a myriad of institutions across different countries work together. Adhering to the same SOPs and policies is essential for creating and maintaining a robust and functional system across the entire network of national nodes. A compliance assessment verifies the conformity of the processes to the relevant SOPs and policies. It represents one step in the GDI Compliance Framework (the "Compliance Framework") which also covers steps such as implementation and training. All elements of the Compliance Framework slot together in a cycle which helps to maintain and continuously improve the system (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Elements of the GDI Compliance Framework.

SOPs and Policies (Figure 1, Step 1) are the backbone of the Compliance Framework. It is necessary for the senior leadership, those in charge of national nodes, to demonstrate commitment to the Compliance Framework (Step 2). Firstly, by nominating representatives to the Operations Committee (OC)⁵ and Security and Data Protection Committee (SDPC)⁵, participating in the approval process as required, and by setting priorities for their teams in terms of providing training in SOPs to node staff (Step 3). It is also important for node representatives to engage with other compliance-related activities, such as creating or implementing SOPs (Step 4) and participating in compliance assessments (Step 5). Monitoring the adherence to SOPs using compliance assessments will highlight areas where processes could or must be improved (Step 6). Periodically executing the steps of the Compliance Framework will lead to regular revisions and improvements of GDI SOPs and Policies, closing a cycle which ensures continuous improvement and node excellence. Ultimately, this will build trust with GDI users that their data will be managed safely and FAIRly.

Both SOPs and Policies will be crucial to GDI operations. The GDI Policies are to be defined as part of the FitSM implementation. The FitSM standards facilitate a lightweight approach to quality service management in IT service provision². One major milestone towards FitSM implementation is the

FitSM training of representatives from all nodes, planned for the end of November 2025. For now, this document focuses on compliance with SOPs, and it will be reviewed for milestone 14 due in 2026.

5. Step-by-step Progression towards SOP Compliance

This section provides a flexible, step-by-step guidance for national nodes to engage with the GDI SOP ecosystem and the Compliance Framework, irrespective of their level of maturity. Some nodes are linked to existing infrastructures that already provide services with an established quality management system, possibly within a certified environment (e.g., ISO 27001), or under contractual obligations (defined by Service Level Agreements). Other nodes are based within an academic environment or are establishing new services and infrastructures with little experience in a compliance framework. By breaking the journey towards SOP Compliance down into incremental steps, each node can progress at their own pace and according to their level of maturity. This allows all nodes jointly moving towards establishing robust services to high quality standards across the GDI network.

Initial steps include engagement with the GDI SOP system, such as connecting to the GDI-SOP GitHub repository. More advanced steps include concepts such as SOP compliance assessment and reporting. These steps are depicted and described below (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Step-by-step guide towards establishing a solid basis for compliance.

5.1. Connect to GDI-SOP GitHub repository and set up a GDI SOP repository branch for your node.

The GDI-SOP GitHub repository is the source-of-truth resource to request, modify and maintain GDI-related SOPs. It provides the necessary support for version control and tracking of actions relating to the documents.

- 5.1.1. Become a member of the GDI GitHub organisation by requesting an invitation from one of the GDI GitHub organisation owners listed on GitHub⁶.
- 5.1.2. Familiarise yourself with how to use the GDI GitHub repository for SOPs by following the introduction document for GDI SOP Maintainers⁷ and watching the recorded video⁸.
- 5.1.3. Follow the instructions in the introduction document above (5.1.2.) to create a GDI-SOP GitHub repository branch for your GDI node, which is necessary to engage with processes like creating, reviewing or modifying SOPs.
- 5.1.4. Read the "GDI-SOP charter"⁹, the "GDI SOP Accessioning Proposal"¹⁰ and the "SOP creation" SOP (GDI-SOP0007)¹¹.

⁶ <https://github.com/orgs/GenomicDataInfrastructure/people?query=role%3Aowner>

⁷ https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/standard-operating-procedures/blob/c26011da5b618259c9adb2d3744533968984729/docs/GDI-SOP_github-introduction-for-maintainers.md

⁸ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bEckeSBS4k7-64QWVyoNrZEW/hGJZxnpw/view?usp=drive_link

⁹ https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/standard-operating-procedures/blob/c26011da5b618259c9adb2d3744533968984729/docs/GDI-SOP_charter.md

¹⁰ https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/standard-operating-procedures/blob/c26011da5b618259c9adb2d3744533968984729/docs/GDI-SOP_sop-accessioning.md#sop-life-cycle

¹¹ https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/standard-operating-procedures/blob/c26011da5b618259c9adb2d3744533968984729/sops/european-level/GDI-SOP0007_sop-template-creation.md

5.2. Implement EU-wide GDI SOPs

In order to implement a coherent system, functioning seamlessly across the GDI network, it is important for some key processes to be implemented identically across all nodes. These "EU-wide SOPs" relate to, for example, the process for creating an SOP¹¹.

- 5.2.1. To ensure that the most up-to-date version of the SOP is being used, check the current list of EU-wide SOPs. These can be accessed through the GitHub folder "sops/european-level"¹².
- 5.2.2. For each EU-wide SOP, determine which member(s) of staff need to be trained and arrange training as appropriate.

5.3. Implement node-specific GDI SOPs

While EU-wide GDI SOPs cover processes that are the same for all nodes, "node-specific SOPs" accommodate node-to-node variability in operations, services, infrastructure, resources, pre-existing processes or other local requirements. As explained in GDI-SOP0007¹¹, node-specific SOPs are based on EU-wide templates which provide a necessary basic alignment for node-specific SOPs describing the same process.

- 5.3.1. To ensure that the most up-to-date version of the SOP is being used, node-specific SOP templates can be accessed through the GitHub folder "sops/node-specific"¹³.
- 5.3.2. If a new node-specific SOP needs to be created, follow GDI-SOP0007¹¹ to create and issue an appropriate SOP to your node's requirements.
- 5.3.3. For each node-specific SOP, determine which member of staff needs to be trained and arrange training as appropriate.

¹²

<https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/standard-operating-procedures/tree/c260111da5b618259c9adb2d3744533968984729/sops/european-level>

¹³

<https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/standard-operating-procedures/tree/c260111da5b618259c9adb2d3744533968984729/sops/node-specific>

5.4. Regular Review of SOPs

It is important to ensure that SOPs accurately reflect how processes are carried out, therefore they need to be reviewed regularly to ensure that they are up-to-date.

- 5.4.1. Contribute to the review of documents when prompted to do so. Automated reminders are set up in GitHub to trigger an annual review of each SOP, as defined in GDI-SOP0007¹¹ and the "Procedures for Information Service Management for SOPs" document¹⁴.
- 5.4.2. When using an SOP on a routine basis, take note of any discrepancies or deviations from the SOP and request modifications as appropriate by raising an issue in the GDI-SOP GitHub repository. This will help to keep the SOPs up-to-date at all times.

5.5. Review of Training Processes and Staff Training Records

All SOPs should be clear, precise, and easy to follow. Nevertheless, it is good practice to train all staff in those SOPs which they follow as part of their job. This ensures that processes are fully understood and carried out consistently, minimising person-to-person variability. By documenting such training in Staff Training Records, diligence is demonstrated, and the records count as evidence towards SOP compliance.

- 5.5.1. Provide staff training in person, online or via a video. The training should be provided by a person familiar with the SOP that is the subject of the training, such as the SOP's co-author, reviewer, or other staff previously trained in the SOP.
- 5.5.2. Document the training in a consistent, auditable, and sustainable way. Annex 1 shows an example of a spreadsheet format that can be used.
- 5.5.3. As a member of staff involved with GDI, you are responsible for maintaining your own training records to ensure they remain up-to-date.
- 5.5.4. Review staff training records as part of the formal SOP compliance assessment. Training records should be reviewed by a more senior member of staff (e.g. line manager) at least once a year to identify any potential gaps or training needs.

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https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/standard-operating-procedures/blob/c260111da5b618259c9adb2d3744533968984729/docs/GDI-SOP_information-service-management.md#73-gdi-sop-review-and-revision

5.6. SOP compliance assessment

A compliance assessment is a systematic evaluation of processes and is key to the continued improvement of a service or processes. This is crucial to maintain a high level of standard, to ensure alignment with defined quality standards, policies or relevant regulations, and to support the ambition to deliver the best possible service, striving for excellence. The compliance assessment can cover a range of aspects as listed below. Depending on the complexity of the system to be audited, the scope of an assessment can be kept broad or focus specifically on certain processes or areas within the system (e.g. Helpdesk processes, or staff training records).

- 5.6.1. Each node is responsible for locally carrying out self-assessments of their processes.
- 5.6.2. The compliance assessment should be performed regularly¹⁵. The scope of an assessment could be kept broad across the node's services, or alternatively, it could be broken down into more frequent, shorter assessments, each focused on a specific aspect, process, or topic.
- 5.6.3. All compliance assessments need to be documented by capturing:
 - 5.6.3.1. Which aspects, processes, or topics were assessed,
 - 5.6.3.2. What the findings were, noting all discrepancies and non-compliances. Annex 2 provides a checklist detailing important aspects to be monitored as part of the assessment.
- 5.6.4. Each assessment must check that all relevant SOPs have been implemented and the latest version of the SOP is being used.
- 5.6.5. Review all processes carried out at the node and check that:
 - 5.6.5.1. There is a GDI SOP available to describe this process,
 - 5.6.5.2. This SOP is implemented at the node,
 - 5.6.5.3. The way the process is carried out is as described in the SOP.
 - 5.6.5.4. If the SOP requires additional documentation (spreadsheets or checklists) to be completed during the process, verify that these are completed, recorded, and securely stored.
 - 5.6.5.5. Check that all staff involved in the process have been trained in the relevant SOPs.

¹⁵ Frequency to be agreed by the OC & SDPC by the end of the project, or next milestone (MS14).

5.7. Assessment Follow-up: Report and Action Plan

The notes made during the assessment should be reviewed and summarised in a report, and an action plan to address deficiencies included, if necessary. To document the node's continued engagement with the GDI Compliance Framework, these reports should be deposited on the GDI shared drive. Annex 3 shows the template for such a report and action plan. It covers the following aspects:

- 5.7.1. Basic information about the compliance assessment:
 - 5.7.1.1. The node,
 - 5.7.1.2. The date of the compliance assessment,
 - 5.7.1.3. The name(s) of the assessor(s),
 - 5.7.1.4. The name of the person completing the report (ideally the same person as the assessor),
 - 5.7.1.5. The signature of the person completing the report, and
 - 5.7.1.6. The date of the signature.

- 5.7.2. Additional details about the compliance assessment's focus, relating to point 5.6.2:
 - 5.7.2.1. There is a tickbox to indicate that it was a major (broad) compliance assessment across the entire range of the node's activities.
 - 5.7.2.2. If the node opted for more frequent but focused compliance assessment, there is a tickbox to indicate that it was a minor compliance assessment and options to specify the specific focus of the compliance assessment.

- 5.7.3. There is a box to list all SOPs which were referred to during the assessment.
- 5.7.4. The remainder of the report form captures the findings of the compliance assessment.
- 5.7.5. Occasionally, a compliance assessment may not observe any deviations or non-compliances when the actual activities are compared to the formal SOPs. This can be captured by the tickbox "The assessment was satisfactory, no corrective actions are needed."

- 5.7.6. The table captures individual observations and an evaluation of risks any potential deviations or non-compliances could pose, also if any corrective or preventive actions are needed to avoid such non-compliances or how to improve the process or system. The table provides fields to capture the following aspects of the observation:
 - 5.7.6.1. The process (step) or activity which was assessed.
 - 5.7.6.2. The relevant SOP(s) for this activity.
 - 5.7.6.3. Under "Observation / Discrepancy", any observations should be captured. This could be:
 - a description of the discrepancy that was observed between the actual activity and the process described in the SOP,
 - no discrepancies observed or

- no relevant SOP available for this activity.
- 5.7.6.4. Severity indicates the level of impact this non-compliance may have
 - high (for example if the non-compliance would affect data protection, security, or significantly affects the quality of the service provided),
 - medium (leading to minor mistakes that can be easily rectified),
 - low (an observation on how a process can be improved).
- 5.7.6.5. The "Comments" field provides additional space to elaborate further on the observation or context.
- 5.7.6.6. "Risks" should be captured if the non-compliance would affect the quality of service, data protection/security risks, or lead to any other significant impact.
- 5.7.6.7. Any recommendations based on the observation should be recorded under "Recommended Mitigation / Corrective Actions". This could include suggestions such as additional training for staff, requesting a new SOP, revising existing SOP, escalating the issue if severe, or rectifying any mistakes made.
- 5.7.6.8. If Action Items are suggested in 5.7.6.7, define (1) who should be responsible for implementing the action & (2) the expected timeline for the action to be completed by.
- 5.7.6.9. Once the action is completed, the date of completion is recorded in the field "Completion Date (to be completed when actioned)".

6. Next steps

The Compliance Framework described above will be the foundation for Milestone 14, the Compliance Assessment planned for 2026.

We are committed to a close collaboration between the GDI tasks 4.2 "European Operations" and 4.3 "SOPs". Task 4.2 is working towards the adoption of FitSM by national nodes within the next six months, starting with FitSM training scheduled for the end of November. As part of the FitSM implementation, GDI policies will be defined. The task 4.3 team will closely monitor the impact of FitSM on SOP requirements and how it can be integrated into the Compliance Framework.

Depending on these observations, this document may be reviewed and extended prior to the Compliance Assessment planned for MS14.

6. Annex 1

Staff Training Records

Name:

Job Title:

Start Date:

Name of Process	SOP accession	SOP version	Comment	Training Start Date	Competency Date	Trainer's Signature	Trainee's Signature
Creation of SOP	SOP0007	v1.0	← Just an example →	DD/MM/YYYY	DD/MM/YYYY	XY	ABC

7. Annex 2

Done?	Prompts:
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are the relevant staff members part of the GDI-SOP GitHub repository so that they can interact with the GDI-SOP GitHub repository (request, review or create SOPs)?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Has the node created a new forkbranch for the GDI-SOP GitHub Repo?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Has your node nominated a member for the GDI Operations Committee (OC)?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Has your node nominated a member for the GDI Security & Data Protection Committee (SDPC)?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Have all relevant EU-wide SOPs been implemented at the node?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Has the node implemented relevant node-specific SOPs?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are you using the most up-to-date version of the SOPs?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are you providing training to the staff when they are new to SOPs?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are you providing training to the staff after an SOP has been updated?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are everyone's training records up-to-date?

Referring to the SOP Compliance Assessment:

- Choose the frequency of compliance assessments (a broad scope annually or more focused, several times per year)??
 - Schedule assessments & choose the topic for each assessment.
 - During the assessment, choose a set of processes relating to the topic, then follow the activities step by step and compare them to the description of the process in the SOP.
 - Make notes of any discrepancies.
-
- After the assessment, refer to the notes from the assessment and complete the Compliance Assessment Report & Action Plan.

8. Annex 3

Compliance Assessment Report & Action Plan

to be completed after the Compliance Assessment

Name of the Assessor: **5.7.1.3**

Person completing this form: **5.7.1.4**

Node: **5.7.1.1**

Date of the Assessment: **5.7.1.2**

Signature: **5.7.1.5**

Date of signature: **5.7.1.6**

blue numbers refer to sections in the text

Focus of the Compliance Assessment:

Major assessment across the node's activities?
 Minor assessment with primary focus on...

- Yes **5.7.2.1**
- Receiving Data **5.7.2.2**
- Loading Data
- Helpdesk
- Data Access
- Training records
- Other:

The assessment covered processes relating to the following SOPs: please list SOP accessions incl. version

5.7.3

5.7.4 Findings:

The assessment was satisfactory, no corrective actions are needed.

5.7.5

- Yes
- No - please see details in table below.

5.7.6 The following observations were made:

Process / Activity reviewed	Related SOP	Observation / Discrepancy	Severity	Comment	Associated Risks	Recommended Mitigation / Corrective Action	Person responsible for Action Item	Date to be completed by	Completion Date (to be completed when actioned)
5.7.6.1	5.7.6.2	5.7.6.3	5.7.6.4	5.7.6.5	5.7.6.6	5.7.6.7	5.7.6.8	5.7.6.8	5.7.6.9
							(1)	(2)	

